

Spectroscopic studies of molecular interactions involving aniline and substituted aniline donors and chloranil as an electron acceptor in a binary solvent mixtures

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Charge-transfer complexes of chloranil acceptor with aniline and substituted anilines as donors were studied in binary solvent mixtures of different composition of benzene and dichloromethane (by volume) at room temperature. The stoichiometry of the complexes was established to be 1 : 1. For this purpose, optical data were subjected to the form of the Rose-Drago equation for 1 : 1 equilibria. The stoichiometry was also tested by other methods such as Scott, Scatchard in addition to Bensi-Hildebrand method. The formation constant (k_c) and molar absorptivities (ϵ_λ) of complexes were determined by least square method. Linear relationship was found between oscillator strength (f) and refractive index function $n^2-1/2n^2 + 1$. The values of $h\nu_{CT}$ were correlated with ionization potential of the donor and a linear relationship was obtained with a slope approximating to unity allowing the determination of the energy of interaction in the excited state. Charge-transfer (CT) band maxima of complexes show red shifts in passing from primary \rightarrow secondary \rightarrow tertiary amines.

Charge-transfer complexes are known to form between donors having sufficiently low ionization potential and acceptors having sufficiently high electron affinity, when the transfer of an electron from donor to acceptor is readily possible¹. It was reported that chloranil form 1 : 1 stoichiometric complexes with alicyclic n-donors viz. piperidine, piperazine and morpholine. Das and Basu² studied spectra of charge-transfer (CT) complexes of anthracene, pyrene, naphthalene and phenanthrene with chloranil, bromanil and iodanyl and reported geometry of the complexes. Charan Singh and Venkateshwarlu³ studied molecular complexes of paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride) and chloranil with phenylhydrazones spectrophotometrically in methanol together with those of paraquat in aqueous SDS micellar media, and reported CT spectra, thermodynamic parameters and stability constants of the complexes. Shrivastava and Verma⁴ have showed conductometrically that stoichiometry of chloranil-aniline complex was 1 : 1 and that of chloranil-pyridine complex was 2 : 3 in methyl alcohol. Thus, stoichiometry of the complex depends on the electron donating ability of the donor and on the electron affinity of the acceptor.

The present investigation involving the well known acceptor, chloranil and their interaction with aniline and substituted anilines were undertaken to establish the stoichiometry of the complexes formed. These studies were made in binary solvent mixtures of benzene and dichloromethane

(by volume) of various compositions at room temperature. The formation constant k_c , molar absorptivities ϵ_λ , oscillator strength f and refractive indices of the complexes were determined. Charge-transfer band maxima of complexes show red shifts in passing from primary \rightarrow secondary \rightarrow tertiary amines.

Experimental

Tetrachloro-*p*-benzoquinone (Chloranil) (B.D.H.) was recrystallized twice from chloroform and was vacuum sublimed and purity checked by TLC³. Aniline (B.D.H.), *o*-toluidine (USSR, A.R. grade), *m*-toluidine (Veb. Jena Pharm, Germany), *N*-methylaniline (B.D.H.), *N,N*-dimethylaniline (B.D.H.), *N,N*-diethylaniline (Riedel) were dried for several hours over caustic potash (B.D.H., A.R. grade) pellets and distilled freshly under reduced pressure just before use. Dichloromethane and benzene from Sarabai Merck were fractionally distilled and only the middle fraction was collected in each case and stored in amber colored bottles. The physical constants such as boiling points and refractive indices were compared with the literature values.

All solutions were prepared by dissolving known weight of acceptor and donors in calibrated flasks. Solutions of donors and acceptor were mixed just before recording the spectra. Spectra were recorded by using Hitachi-330 double beam recording spectrophotometer. The optical density was read with an accuracy of $\pm 0.002\%$. The wavelength was

read with an accuracy of ± 0.2 nm. The desired temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The absorption spectra of complexes were recorded at low scan speed. The solutions were allowed to attain thermal equilibrium before optical measurements were made. Spectral measurements were made with acceptor concentration of 1×10^{-3} M, which was kept constant and the concentration of the donor was varied. While recording the spectra, pure solvent was used in the reference cell.

Results and discussion

Spectrum of the acceptor was recorded in binary mixtures of benzene and dichloromethane (by volume) of different composition at room temperature and it was noticed that the acceptor had no absorption in the visible region below 500 nm. The donors were colorless when freshly distilled and hence show no absorption in the region given above. But on mixing the solutions of the donor and the acceptor in a chosen mixture of solvents characteristic color was developed which had an absorption band. This indicates the formation of charge-transfer complex. For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex the optical data were subjected to Rose-Drago treatment⁵, because the Bensi-Hildebrand (B-H) treatment⁶ was found to be inadequate. As per Rose-Drago treatment the expression for the 1 : 1 stoichiometry is

$$C_A^0 \cdot C_D^0 / d = 1 / k_c^{AD} \cdot \epsilon_\lambda^{AD} + C_A^0 + C_D^0 / \epsilon_\lambda^{AD}$$

where C_A^0 and C_D^0 are the initial concentrations of the acceptor and the donor respectively. d is the measured optical density of the complex, k_c is the formation constant of the complex and ϵ_λ is the molar absorptivity of the complex. According to this equation the plots $C_A^0 \cdot C_D^0 / d$ vs $C_A^0 + C_D^0$ should be a straight line. Actually our experimental results

when plotted gave straight line clearly indicating the 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the complex. Fig. 1 shows typical Rose-Drago (1 : 1) plot for chloranil-*N,N*-dimethylaniline mixture (61.96B + 38.04D%) by volume at 26°C . Thus the stoichiometry of the complexes were established as 1 : 1 in all chosen mixture of the solvents studied.

From the slopes and intercepts of the plots, the formation constant k_c and the molar absorptivities ϵ_λ of the complexes have been evaluated in binary mixtures of benzene and dichloromethane (Table 1). Stoichiometry was also tested and confirmed by other method such as Scott⁷ and Scatchard⁸ in addition to Bensi-Hildebrand.

Fig. 1. Rose-Drago (1 : 1) plot for chloranil *N,N*-dimethylaniline complex in benzene and dichloromethane mixture (61.96B + 38.04D%) by volume at 26°C .

Table 1. Chloranil-*N,N*-dimethylaniline complex in mixed solvents (benzene + dichloromethane) at 26°C

Sr. no.	Solvent composition % vol.	Range of donor concentration (M)	k_c	ϵ_λ	Refractive index	λ_{max} (nm)	$f \times 10^2$	μ_{EN} Debyes
1.	Dichloromethane (100%)	0.10–0.45	1.2339	2175.80	1.4250	655	5.6187	2.7968
2.	14.86B + 85.14D	0.10–0.45	1.2166	1984.52	1.4275	654	5.5385	2.7767
3.	28.20B + 71.80D	0.10–0.45	1.1224	1964.63	1.4415	653	5.4404	2.7521
4.	40.96B + 59.04D	0.10–0.45	1.0327	1931.62	1.4500	652	5.3791	2.7261
5.	51.72B + 48.28D	0.10–0.45	0.9830	1913.14	1.4585	651	5.3262	2.7126
6.	61.96B + 38.04D	0.10–0.80	0.8932	1899.69	1.4640	650	5.3081	2.7080
7.	70.83B + 29.17D	0.10–0.45	0.8285	1852.53	1.4710	649	5.2699	2.6879
8.	79.00B + 21.00D	0.15–0.50	0.7723	1851.85	1.4780	648	5.1884	2.6670
9.	86.67B + 13.33D	0.15–0.50	0.7337	1865.32	1.4820	647	5.1507	2.6573
10.	93.58B + 06.42D	0.15–0.50	0.6884	1902.22	1.4900	646	5.2102	2.6726
11.	Benzene (100%)	0.10–0.80	0.6093	1877.22	1.5010	645	5.0663	2.6355

Refractive indices of each solvent mixture and of pure solvents were determined by Abbe's refractometer and were tabulated in Table 1. It was observed that as the volume of benzene in dichloromethane increases the values of formation constant k_c and molar absorptivities ϵ_λ decreases. Similarly λ_{\max} values are also found to be decreased. The oscillator strength and transition moments were calculated and have been given in Table 1.

Many workers have shown that oscillator strength f is some function of refractive index of solvent. Weigang and Wild⁹ reported a linear relation between oscillator strength f and refractive index function $n^2 - 1/2n^2 + 1$. In our present study the oscillator strength f for the system of chloranil-*N,N*-dimethylaniline in binary solvent mixture of various composition gives linear relationship f and $n^2 - 1/2n^2 + 1$ (Fig. 2). Similarly the plot of k_c vs λ_{CT} was found to be linear.

Fig. 2. Variation of oscillatory strength f with refractive index function $(n^2 - 1/2n^2 + 1)$ for the system of chloranil-*N,N*-dimethylaniline complex in a binary solvent mixture of benzene and dichloromethane of various composition.

It is well known that *p*-benzoquinones are π -acceptors¹⁰, whose electron affinities are enhanced by the introduction of electron withdrawing groups such as chloro, nitro and cyano on the *p*-benzoquinone moiety¹¹. Chloranil as π ac-

ceptor has been selected due to high electron affinity i.e. 1.37/2.40 eV^{1,12} and in view of its potential utility as a fungicide¹³. Although one may expect that aniline or *N*-alkylaniline to act as n -donors, using the *N*-atom lone pair electrons the very same electrons are involved in an intramolecular $n\pi$, $a\pi$ interaction between the NR₂ or NH₂ group and the C₆H₅ group¹⁴. Even if these π -island electrons are not involved in conjugation with the ring, the lone pair electrons are an almost π -island which take part in an intermolecular charge-transfer action as a π -donor¹⁵. Therefore the charge-transfer complex formed by the interaction of chloranil acceptor with substituted aniline donors are of $b\pi$ - $a\pi$ type, where the electron transfer involves loss of a bonding electron from the $b\pi$ -donor and gain of antibonding electron by the an acceptor.

The linear dependence of charge-transfer energy $h\nu_{CT}$, on the ionization potential I^D of the donors has been examined by using the approximate relation¹⁶.

$$h\nu_{CT} = aI^D + b$$

where a and b are some constants. For a series of complexes with a common acceptor Mc Connell *et al.*¹⁶ suggested the following equation relating the charge-transfer energy and ionization potential

$$h\nu_{CT} = I^D - E^A - W$$

where E^A is the electron affinity of the acceptor and W is the dissociation energy of the charge-transfer excited state. This relationship was employed for the determination of the ionization potentials of relatively weak donors. It gives a linear plot of $h\nu_{CT}$ against I^D although the linearity was questionable over a wide range of I^D ¹⁷. From this expression the values of dissociation energies of charge-transfer excited state were calculated for the complexes studied. The calculated values for the complexes of chloranil acceptor with aniline and substituted aniline donors were tabulated in Table 2. The ionization potentials of several of the donors employed in this investigation were available from the studies of molecular complexes of aniline with chloranil¹⁸.

Table 2. Complexes of chloranil acceptor with aniline and substituted aniline donors

Sr. no.	Donor	Solvent composition	C_D^0 (M)	λ_{\max} (nm)	I^D (eV)	$h\nu_{CT}$	W (eV)
1.	<i>N,N</i> -Diethylaniline	61.9B + 38.04D	0.15–1.210	730	6.99	1.6977	3.9223
2.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline	61.96B + 38.04D	0.10–0.80	650	7.20	1.9037	3.9263
3.	<i>N</i> -Methylaniline	61.96B + 38.04D	0.15–1.20	570	7.53	2.1765	3.9835
4.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	61.96B + 38.04D	0.10–0.80	546	7.62	2.2721	3.9779
5.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	61.96B + 38.04D	0.10–0.80	540	7.66	2.2973	3.9927
6.	Aniline	61.96B + 38.04D	0.15–0.20	519	7.77	2.3903	3.9397

Since a plot of I^D against $h\nu_{CT}$ was found to be linear in complexes of iodine¹⁶, 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene¹⁹ and chloranil¹⁹ for a number of donors, it may be considered as independent of the nature of the donor¹⁶. Our result also gave straight line plot (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Dependence of the charge-transfer energy ($h\nu_{CT}$) upon the ionization potential of the donor (I^D) for complexes of chloranil acceptor in benzene and dichloromethane solvent mixture (61.96B + 38.04D% by volume i.e. 50–50% by weight) at room temperature : (1) *N,N*-diethylaniline, (2) *N,N*-dimethylaniline, (3) *o*-toluidine, (4) *m*-toluidine, (5) aniline.

This figure and Table 2 shows that the lower the ionization potential of the electron donor, the smaller is the transition energy of the charge-transfer band as expected from Mulliken's theory¹⁴.

For the distinction and the determination of the amines one does not need to resolve the charge-transfer bands and the determination can be done directly utilizing the CT band maxima listed in Table 2. It is clear from the λ_{max} values that gradual red shifts are obtained in passing from primary to tertiary amines.

Conclusion : The stoichiometry of the complexes of tetrachloro-*p*-benzoquinone (chloranil) acceptor with aniline and substituted anilines was established as 1 : 1 in binary solvent mixtures of benzene and dichloromethane

in the chosen range of donor and acceptor concentrations. Linear relationship was found between oscillator strength f and refractive index function $n^2 - 1/2n^2 + 1$ as well as k_c and λ_{CT} . Charge-transfer (CT) band maxima of complexes show red shifts in passing from primary to tertiary amines.

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